

Article

Rural Markets: The Case of Silcoorie Yearly Mela Market

Dr. Joydeep Goswami*

Abstract

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8302332

In this paper, the author has discussed the role of markets in rural society through a case study of Silcoorie Yearly Mela market.

Key terms

Market, shopkeepers, customers, mela

Rural market in Indian economy plays an important role in the lives of the masses. Since ancient times, Indian villages had the concept of village market popularly known as 'Haats'. Village 'Mandis' and yearly 'Mela' are other important occasion for the marketers to tap. In recent times after Green Revolution, rural markets have acquired great significance, as the overall growth of the economy has resulted in substantial increase in purchasing power of the rural communities. In India other than the metropolitan cities, all the districts and towns are concerned about the rural markets. The rural market in India is not a separate entity itself and is highly influenced by the sociological and behavioural factors working in the country. In the era of liberalization and globalization a revolution has taken place in rural India which has compelled the marketers to reach to rural India.

The competition is shifting from urban cities to rural areas and villages. The yearly *Mela* market are not just a number of huts huddled together where the transactions between the buyers and sellers take place on the days of a season.

* The author is Organizing Secretary, Netaji Chitra Yuva Sangstha (NCYS) and Field Research Investigator in a project sponsored by ICSSR

It plays an important role in the rural economy because these markets serve as the main channels through which the local products and commodities brought from outside are exchanged or sold. The rural market may be developing and it faces some problems such as low per capita income, dependence on the monsoon, seasonal demand, poor communication, power problem and storage problem etc. The study introduces the execution scheme of the study conducted on the yearly *Mela* market of Silcoorie village in the Cachar district of Assam to understand the socio-economic condition, market structures and its impact.

Rural Markets: A Review of the Literature

In this section, we offer a survey of the extant literature. Let us begin by defining the concept of market. According to Scott and Marshall, "in both economics and sociology a market is understood to be an area over which any well defined commodity is exchanged between buyers and sellers"**. A large number of studies have been done on rural markets. Among the social scientists who have made general studies of markets are Acharya and Agrawal (Acharya, 1999), Dutta, M., Balakrishnan, and Dey (Dutta, 1995), A.K.Ganguly (Ganguly, 1996, pp. 175-176.)A.S.Ganguly (Ganguly A. , 1997). Gopalswamy (Gopalswamy, 2005)

Apart from these general studies, some scholars have studied markets in Assam. Dey studied economic documents of Assam. (Dey.R.Kr., 1988.) S.Ghosh studied the coconut market of Assam. (Ghosh, 1993.) Arora and Pandey studied cattle markets in Haryana. (Arora, 1992) .From these studies , we may conclude that there exist a large body of literature on markets and it is growing.

** John Scott and Gordon Marshall, "Market " John Scott and Gordon Marshall eds *Oxford Dictionary of Sociology*, Third Edition Revised, Oxford University Press, 2009, p.437

Methodology of the Study

The study is based on primary data collected from the respondents (sellers and buyers) drawn from the Silcoorie *Mela* market which constitutes the universe of the study and the sellers and buyers of these markets constitute its units for data collection and analysis. The market has been purposively selected so as to understand the rural market in this part of the country. From the market two types of respondents; namely, sellers (50) and buyers (50) who were available were selected by using a combination of accidental and purposive sampling methods for collection of their oral responses. Therefore, while selecting the respondents of both the categories even accidentally it was purposively endeavored to represent the shopkeepers and customers from all communities and castes in the sample. An interview schedule was administered to the respondents during October 13th 2013 to October 18th 2013.

Locale of the study

The Silcoorie market is 12 km from Silchar, the head quarter and town of the Cachar district. A metalled road from Silchar to Hailakandi passes through the market. Close to this market is located the Post Office the place known as Silcoorie Dakghar. Yearly market is a gathering of people exchanging products and services as in most cases people of rural areas are participating in the yearly market. There is no written document on the origin and growth of the market. According to local sources, the market was started in 1904 on the occasion of *Rasha Purnima* and it was also known as *Baram Babar* (The Lord Vishnu) *Mela*. In the beginning, there were no stalls in this market. The villagers and garden labourers sat in the open place with their goods. There were only a few shops as well as buyers of goods. But along with the development and the increasing demand of goods and popularity of *Baram Baba* (The Lord Vishnu) among the people the market has grown as the biggest *Mela* (yearly fair-cum-market) of Chatla area. The seasonal markets like the Silcoorie market refers to a place where the buyers, sellers apart from buying and selling of their commodities enjoy some services, available in the market during transaction days. In Silcoorie market the people have the opportunity to meet the experts of

diversified occupations such as cobblers, barbers, local medical practitioners, mechanics, *tantrics* and astrologers from the different parts of Barak Valley and West Bengal. The Astrologers provide stones and *kabach* (Amulet) etc. The *Tantrics* do pooja of *Shakti* (Goddesses of Power) on request, and barbers and cobblers provide services during the market days and they are from the Other Backward Castes, local medical practitioners provide *bonaji* (Ayurvedic) medicine to the villagers. Apart from these, there is provision for entertainment such as *charkhi* (Catherine Wheel), dance, *putul nach* (puppetry) and magic show. These are the main attraction of the *mela*. People visit the *mela* and prefer to watch dance, and puppetry. Children and the young visitors from both the gender like to sit on the Catherine wheel and enjoy the thrill. The market consists of about 250 to 300 shops and 20-25 stalls, approximately, of grocery, stationery, tea stalls, cosmetics, chat house, tattoo designing, garments shop etc. The distribution of the shop is shown in the following diagram:

Social Organisation of the Market

The yearly market (*mela*) is the place where people from both the genders and from various places gather and share their ideas and the market function for exchange of political ideas, economic goods and socio-cultural patterns among the people. The exchanges of ideas in the market motivate the farmers to use improved scientific methods of production and distribution as well as proper use of resources and markets. The market can motivate the people of that area for their positive involvement, which generate avenues for economic development of the area. Apart from the economic aspects Silcoorie market (*Baram Babar Mela*) serves variety of social functions and plays an important role in the social life of the people. Of the various units of its social organization, of the shopkeepers and customers are used in the following discussion to understand the way each of the two units organize the Silcoorie market:

The Shopkeepers

Shopkeeper manages and owns a shop/unit of market. He/she serves the customers by selling commodities and also maintains relations with the customers. Barring a small fraction of females from

SCs and OBCs all the shopkeepers in Silcoorie market are Bengali and Bhojpuri males and most of them belong to the middle age group and large families.

availability of fire wood and low cost of kerosene in comparison to gas stoves. The shopkeepers are not

Source: Field Survey Conducted from October 13th 2013 to October 18th 2013

The village is dominated by the Bengali people followed by the tea garden labourers most of them are OBCs. The shopkeeper's family income ranges from less than Rs 41000 to 140000 and above but most of them belong to the income bracket of Rs 41000-100000, because the shopkeepers belong to the medium size and large size families and all the members of the family are not engaged in any activities. So, the per capita income of the family is low. Most of the shopkeepers are local and a few are migrated. Tea garden population have their own Assam type bamboo and mud walls with tin roof, semi-RCC, Assam type half brick walls with bamboo and tin roof and Assam type bamboo walls and thatched roof houses with two or three living rooms facilitated with drinking water, electricity, gas stove, necessary and luxury households. The village has two Public Health Engineering Offices and the village is covered by the community tap and community well. These are the main sources of drinking water in the village. All the shopkeepers use *chulha* while over half (52%) of them use kerosene stove because of the

able to afford the cost to use gas stove. Shopkeepers have access to mass media such as news papers TV Radio and Mobile for recreation and contacts but the access to print media (news papers) is very low among the shopkeepers. All the female shopkeepers are not accessing the modern media because of the poor economic condition.

The Customers

Customers are those who purchase commodities from market and satisfy their necessities. Most of the customers are male and less numbers are female almost all the female customers are Bengali and Bhojpuri, because the villagers are mostly Bengalis and Bhojpuris. Most of the customers are middle age in the age group of 35 – 50 years, because they find their needs in the market. Most of the customers are local and have their own houses and quarters availing the amenities such as electricity, drinking water, sanitation but most of the tea garden and brick industry labourers are not able to avail these amenities, because of the difference in economic conditions. Most of the customers across

all the caste categories have access to mass media such as mobile, TV, Radio etc but the access to print media such as news paper is less among the customers perhaps because of low literacy and availability of other media. The customers are mostly illiterate and the cost of the news papers becomes burden on their families.

Thus, the Silcoorie market is dominated by the Bengali and Bhojpuri male shopkeepers belong to the middle age group. Most of the shopkeepers are local residents of the village by birth and belong to the different income groups and living standard with exposure to mass media. The customers of the markets are the middle aged who belong to different language groups. Most of the customers are local. The shopkeepers and customers of this market belong to different castes such as General Castes, Scheduled Castes, Other Backward Castes and Most Other Backward Castes, age groups such as youths, middle age and old age and language groups such as Bhojpuri, Bengali, Hindi, and Assamese. During transaction shopkeepers and customers from different age group communicate with each other in Bengali or Bhojpuri, as these two languages are the major languages of the valley. Some of the shopkeepers use Hindi for trading with their customers of respective community. Different cultural habits come into contact through this market and cultural transformation and sharing takes place; such as dress, food and participation in the religious occasions and so on. The development of the market has direct and indirect impact on the socio-economic conditions, living standard and media habits of the villagers as well as outsiders.

Structure and Functioning of the Market

The yearly Silcoorie market is the biggest annual event of the Chatla area in the Barak valley. In Silcoorie, the means of communication are poor and literacy is very low. Yet even now in the era of mobile phone (globalization and digitization) Silcoorie *Baram Babar Mela* provides a place of face to face interaction among the rural people of Barak valley. The market comprises some unassuming thatched houses with polythene roof and even in some cases with no walls at all. The yearly markets

like that of Silcoorie are socially structured. The market of Silcoorie is also no exception to this. Its structure consists of various units like shops, shopkeepers, customers, suppliers of goods and visitors. However, in the present discussion, the units; namely, shops, goods, shopkeepers and customers have been used to understand structural and functional patterns of the social organization of the Silcoorie yearly market.

The shops of the market are private and public owned shop (*Nyajjo Muller Dukan*). Most of the shops are of bamboo wall and polythene roof and bamboo and polythene surroundings. The shopkeepers have different sources of power as electricity, oil lamp and other devices with battery. The market was established in 1904 but, most of the shop of the market established their business during the period 1990-2012. The shopkeepers manage the investment on goods as well as fixtures of the shop. The investment made by the shopkeepers ranges from <20000 to 70,000 and above. The market extend within the block has customers from both the gender. The customers of the market are both regular as well as irregular. The shopkeepers have taken loan from different loaning agencies such as bank, micro financial institutions, money-lenders etc to start new business and for the expanding the existing business. The shopkeepers receive the supply daily and on every alternate day through roadways on credit, cash on delivery and cash in advance. The market serves the customers come to the market from distant places. Most of the customers are local and residing within the distance of 1km – 3km. Varieties of product are available in the market but the price and quality differs from other markets. Most of the customers visit favourite shop for good quality and shops lay out.

Thus, the market established in the year 1904 and gradually developed but the pace of development increased during the period 1996-2010. The shops are different from each other in terms of their structure and commodities for transaction. Financial institutions like bank, micro financial institutions grab the opportunity for further investment. The market extends within block and has variety of customers as regular and irregular.

Impact of the Market

The yearly market of Silcoorie has its impact on the economic, social, political, technological and developmental aspects in the rural area. Even as the pace of all round development of the village and the connectivity with the remote places through road led the extension of the volume of business. Apart from this the market has its impact on the infrastructural and institutional development of the village. The expansion and development of the market always reflect the development of the socio-economic condition. Silcoorie market has a wide impact on the society as the increased income and volume of business gives rise to new occupations for a specific period of three to four days. Thus, the local people across the caste categories and genders and age groups show their interest in marketing. They purchase items from remote places and town and sell at a high price and motivate the youth for the seasonal business and the number of shop increased. The *mela* is a yearly gathering and plays a pivotal role in the political aspects. The villagers discussed the matters in the market and motivate others to react on government policies and programmes. Formation of groups, unions and associations has reduced the dependence on political parties and politicians. The modern technologies and machineries have replaced the traditional items and practices of the villagers such as use of electronic gadgets and handmade tattoo being replaced by machine made tattoo. The market has its impact on the institutional and infrastructural development of the village; namely, two primary schools, RCC road construction, community hall construction and so on.

Conclusion

To conclude it can be said that in Barak Valley, rural markets have developed along with the establishment of different social and economic institutions. All the rural markets depend on the urban market for supply of the consumer durables. These markets were mostly established in the British period and gradually developed but the pace of development accelerated during the last twenty years or so ie. from 1990 onwards. The shops are different in terms of their structure and commodities of transaction. Financial institutions like banks, money lenders and microfinance advance loans to these markets. The market extension depends on the type

of its customers. The rural markets in the valley have the potential and future opportunities for the socio-economic development of the rural areas. The markets of Barak valley have considerable impact on the economic, cultural and social lives of the rural peoples. The commodity structure and catchment area of these commodities as well as the participation patterns in the markets clearly reveal the fact that these markets serve most of the basic needs of the rural population in the villages and in their surroundings. These markets have impacts on the social life of the people as the people come into contact with each other, share their thoughts and ideas and relate with one another as of customer and shopkeeper, shopkeeper and shopkeeper, customer and customer and so on.

References

- Acharya, S. a. (1999). *Agricultural marketing in India*. . New Delhi:: Oxford and IBH Publishing Company Private Limited.
- Arora, R. a. (1992). *Marketing costs and margins in cattle trade in Haryana: Agricultural marketing*. (ed.) *Marketing in India: Cases and readings*. New Delhi: Vikash Publishing House PVT LTD.
- Dey.R.Kr. (1988.). *The Barak Valley- A survey of documents on the economic history -1832-1947*. New Delhi: Peoples Publishing House.
- Dutta, M. B. (1995). . *Rural marketing: Myth and reality*. . Delhi: Himalaya Publishing House.
- Ganguly, A. (1997). , The growing rural market in India, . . In N. (ed.), *Marketing in India: Cases and readings*. New Delhi: Vikash Publishing House PVT LTD.
- Ganguly, A. .. (1996). "Rural marketing strategy: Attempts to explore new area", . In. (ed.), *Marketing in India: Cases and readings*. . New Delhi : Vikash Publishing House PVT LTD.
- Ghosh, S. (1993.). . A study of mature coconut market of Assam, *Agricultural marketing*. . In Neelamegham (ed.), *Marketing in India: Cases and readings*. New Delhi: Vikash Publishing House PVT LTD.
- Gopalswamy, T. (2005). . *Rural marketing, environment, problems and strategies*. . New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Private Limited.